

CST4ALL

Support to the Activities of the Concentrated Solar Thermal Technology Area of the SET Plan

CST4ALL Industry Workshop on the hybridisation of Concentrated Solar Thermal Technologies (CST) with heat pumps

Date	29 October 2024
Time	10:00 – 13:00 CET
Online event	Microsoft Teams
Registration link	Available here

Agenda

- 10:00 Welcome and introduction to CST4ALL project and webinar objectives**
Konstantinos Genikomsakis – *European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (ESTELA)*
Yelda Erden Topal – *Middle East Technical University (METU)*
- 10:10 Message from the European Commission**
Philippe Schild – *DG for Research and Innovation, European Commission*
- 10:15 Keynote presentations on hybridisation possibilities of CST and heat pumps**
Yuvaraj Sathiyadev Pandian – *Solarlite CSP Technology GmbH*
Miguel Ramirez – *Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (TNO)*
Pankaj Kumar – *United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO)*
Q&A
- 11:15 Live poll**
- 11:20 Break**
- 11:30 Round table: Industrial maturity of technologies, bankability of projects, regional specific conditions, necessary skills, market potential, manufacturing facilities in Europe and expected R&I contributions**
Moderator:
Maurizio Pieve – *Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA)*
Participants:
Yuvaraj Sathiyadev Pandian – *Solarlite CSP Technology GmbH*

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the European Union**

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Diego Caro Pegalajar – *ACCIONA Industrial*
María Luisa Revilla Trujillo – *Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology (CDTI)*
Cordin Arpagaus – *OST Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences*
Miguel Ramirez – *Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (TNO)*
Andrej Misec – *Association of European Renewable Energy Research Centers (EUREC)*
Paul Kenny – *European Heat Pump Association (EHPA)*

12:50 Wrap-up and conclusions

Peter Heller – *German Aerospace Center (DLR)*

13:00 End of workshop

This CST4ALL project event is organised with the support of the European Technology and Innovation Platform on Renewable Heating & Cooling (RHC-ETIP).

CST4ALL Coordinator

Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.
in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

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